

RNA-seq analysis: reads to differential expression

10 & 11 September 2024

1 - 4:30 pm AEST

Schedule

Timings are approximate and subject to change.

Tuesday 10 September 2024

Time	Topic
12:55pm	Zoom opens for participants
1:00 pm AEST	Welcome and housekeeping Log into Galaxy
1:10 pm AEST	Presentations and follow-along exercises <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mouse mammary gland dataset 2. Preparing the reads <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Import data from URLs 2. Raw reads QC 3. Trim reads 4. Trimmed reads QC 3. Mapping <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Map reads to reference genome
	Discussion time
3 pm AEST (Approx)	Break (15 mins)
3:15 pm AEST	Presentations and follow-along exercises <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Counting

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Count reads mapped to genes 2. Create count matrix 5. Generating a QC summary report <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strandness 2. Duplicate reads 3. Reads mapped to chromosomes 4. Gene body coverage (5'-3') 5. Read distribution across features (exons, introns, intergenic..)
4:15 pm AEST	Discussion time
4:25 pm AEST	Wrap up day 1 and what to expect tomorrow
4:30 pm AEST	End of day 1

Wednesday 11 September 2024

Time	Topic
12:55 pm AEST	Zoom opens for participants
1:00 pm AEST	Welcome back and housekeeping
1:05 pm AEST	Presentations and follow-along exercises <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mouse mammary gland dataset • Preparing the inputs <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Import data 2. Get gene annotations • Differential expression with limma-voom <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Filtering to remove lowly expressed genes 2. Normalization for composition bias 3. Specify Contrast(s) of interest
	Discussion time
3 pm AEST (Approx)	Break
3:15 pm AEST	Presentations and follow-along exercises <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • QC of count data <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Multidimensional scaling plot

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Density plots 3. Box plots 4. Voom variance plot 5. MD and Volcano plots for DE results • Testing relative to a threshold (TREAT) • Visualising results <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Heatmap of top genes 2. Stripcharts of top genes 3. Interactive DE plots (Glimma) • Conclusion
4:00 pm AEST	Discussion time
4:20 pm AEST	Wrap up and feedback
4:30 pm AEST	End of workshop